

Between Tradition and Progress: A Qualitative Exploration of Access Constraints to Higher Education for Marginalized Girls in Hargeisa, Somaliland

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Abstract:

This research qualitatively explores the barriers, both stemming from traditional practices and contemporary challenges that hinder marginalized girls from accessing higher education in Hargeisa, Somaliland. Using purposive and snowball sampling, 22 semi-structured interviews were conducted with parents and girls intimately familiar with the issue. Findings indicate a limited number of marginalized girls in Hargeisa attain university education, with the primary obstructions being socio-economic and socio-cultural in nature. These barriers are deeply entrenched in both age-old traditions and current societal challenges. The study underscores the need for targeted interventions by governmental and tertiary

institutions. Key determinants impacting higher education access include familial financial constraints, parental education and roles, type of pre-tertiary education, lack of female mentors, early marriage customs, prevalent discrimination, and scarce scholarship opportunities. Addressing these factors is pivotal for enhancing educational prospects for marginalized girls in the region.

Keywords: *marginalized girls, higher education, Hargeisa Somaliland, Socio-cultural Barriers, Discrimination.*

Introduction

The transformative power of education, particularly higher education, in shaping societal trajectories is undisputed. The Human Development Index (HDI) and the Gender Development Index (GDI) underscore this, revealing how education, especially for women, catalyzes empowerment and societal progress (Joshi, 2010). Women with higher education not only benefit personally through increased confidence and critical thinking but also

contribute significantly to societal decision-making processes that influence health, career choices, and the education of future generations (Kamath et al., 2020).

The global recognition of education's pivotal role is evident in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which emphasize ending poverty, ensuring quality education, and reducing inequalities. Yet, the reality remains starkly different for marginalized girls, particularly in developing countries. In regions like Kenya, the

barriers are geographic and socio-cultural, with girls in marginalized areas facing stark disparities in educational transition rates (Mokua, 2013). In Somaliland, these challenges are exacerbated by socio-cultural norms, with early marriage trends significantly hindering girls' access to education (Gender in Somalia Brief II, 2015; Jama & Barre, 2019).

Literature Review

Although the gender issue in higher education is not a new phenomenon, it varies from culture and society to society. As a result, a large and growing body of literature has investigated gender marginalization in higher education from a global and national perspective to better understand gender problems in both developed and developing countries.

Almost three decades ago, Chanana (1993) suggested that there is a need to break this inequality when he examined the growth of higher education in the context of preferential treatment and structural reforms such as policies for various social groups, like marginalized communities. For instance, as reported by Salmi & D'Addio (2021) marginalized communities have a significantly lower chance of pursuing higher education. The data indicates that in the majority of nations for which statistics are available, students from marginalized communities had a lower chance of attending university than the general population, based on the results of household surveys in numerous low- and middle-income countries. As a result, social justice and economic efficiency will not be achieved

Several studies investigating sociocultural factors have been carried out in recent years. Most of them have widely investigated the relationship between sociocultural factors and access to higher education for marginalized girls. Factors thought to be influencing access to higher education for marginalized girls have been explored in these studies. On one hand, Singh (2007) found that many young girls in India marry and become mothers before they have the chance to reach their full potential. And that is why only a few students from the poorest and most marginalized communities have access to

higher education. Similarly, in Puntland and Somaliland, Jama & Barre (2019) and NAGAAD (2019) both found that the gap in higher education attainment between men and women runs deep, where social and cultural practices such as early marriage and preferential treatment of boys were identified as major barriers in access to higher education. Several studies have revealed that women graduates are often confused between marrying, having children, working part-time after graduation, or entering high status: they have been heavily influenced by society in either direction (e.g. Polenghi & Fitzgerald, 2020). This theory of women's choice is especially relevant to this study because Somali mindset, raising a family is considered the ultimate goal of a woman's life.

On the other hand, in recent years, there has been increasing research looking into the extent to which women can acquire empowerment through higher education. They revealed that higher education allows women to have an impact on a variety of discriminatory practices at the same time, resulting in positive change. For example, Malik and Courtney (2011) argued that enhancing women's access to higher education enables them to play a bigger role as role models in their families and communities.

A recent study conducted by Tiwari (2020) indicated after the government of India initiated several scholarship programs that these scholarships have a significant impact on females in the state of Haryana although there were several inconsistencies in the eligibility conditions and other requirements that limit the effect of these scholarships.

Overall, access to higher education for women in general, particularly marginalized girls, there seems to be some evidence to indicate that there are surrounding factors for this issue that need to be addressed.

Statement of the Problem

Straddling the line between tradition and progress, Hargeisa, Somaliland stands as a focal point of the tension about marginalized girls' accessibility to higher education. Tradition, with its deep-rooted customs and societal norms,

often acts as a formidable barrier to the aspirations of marginalized girls. Yet, the winds of progress beckon, urging societies to evolve and recognize the undeniable rights and potentials of these girls.

Somaliland, unrecognized and one of the least developed nations, stands as a testament to these challenges. Despite the global push for inclusive education, girls from marginalized communities in Hargeisa, Somaliland, confront deeply rooted societal barriers. Factors like socio-economic disparities, clan-based favoritism, and societal perceptions continue to stifle their educational aspirations (Bosu & Dawson-Amoah, 2018). While there's a breadth of research on women's education in Somaliland, a glaring gap exists concerning the specific challenges faced by marginalized girls (Madar, 2016; NAGAAD, 2019; Pherali & Lewis, 2019).

This study, therefore, isn't just an academic endeavor. It's a call to action. By delving deep into the determinants affecting marginalized girls' access to higher education in Hargeisa, Somaliland, the study seeks to spotlight a pressing issue that demands immediate attention and intervention.

The General Objective of the Study

To qualitatively investigate barriers, rooted in traditional practices and modern challenges hindering marginalized girls' access to higher education in Hargeisa, Somaliland.

Specific Objectives

- To delve into the personal narratives and perceptions of marginalized girls in Hargeisa, Somaliland, examining how socioeconomic status influences their journey towards higher education.
- Understand the implications of scholarship suspensions on the aspirations of marginalized girls for higher education.
- Delve into socio-cultural factors influencing marginalized girls' access to higher education.

Materials and Methods

In this study, a qualitative research design was used and data was collected through semi-structured interviews. Focusing on the nature of this research, purposive and snowball sampling were used to select the research respondents where sampling frame was chosen due to their knowledge of the used research questions relating to access to higher education for marginalized girls and since the data collection process initially was started with a few respondents relevant to the study objectives, these sampled respondents suggest adding additional respondents who have expertise or criteria relevant to the study.

When the data was collected, data management and analysis were performed using qualitative data analysis techniques. Following this, a six-step process of thematic analysis, including familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining themes, and writing up the themes was employed. This process provides an illuminating description of the phenomenon by bringing similar categories together with codes into broader themes to lead to the final themes which link to overarching themes/concepts to gain detailed insights into the phenomenon.

Sample

The study participants were marginalized girls at a university level or who graduated from secondary schools and parents in Hargeisa, Somaliland. With purposive sampling, such as many qualitative studies, 12 interviews should be enough to reach data saturation (Guest et al., 2006). Therefore, 22 interviews (9 parents and 13 girls) were conducted in this qualitative study. The sample size of this study was determined by the data saturation and considering roles such as parents and secondary or university student girls.

Results

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

As presented in Table 1, twenty-two (17 female and 5 male) participants with ages varying between 18 and 56 years were purposively

recruited and were interviewed face-to-face. Ten participants were recruited from parents and 12 from girls who graduated or studying at university or recently graduated from secondary school. All the participants reside in Hargeisa City.

Table 1. Demographic profile of the respondents

	Male (n = 5)	Female (n = 17)
Age Group		
18 – 25	0	5
26 – 33	0	7
34 – 41	0	2
42 – 49	3	3
50+	2	0
Marital Status		
Single	0	12
Married	5	3
Divorced	0	1
Widowed	0	1
Level of Education		
Never attended school	1	1
Primary level	1	2
Secondary level	3	7
University level	0	7
Occupation		
Employed	4	3
Not employed	1	4
Student	0	10

To validate the responses collected from the study participants, thematic analysis was used to gain insights into parents and girls' perspectives regarding access constraints to higher education for marginalized girls in Hargeisa, Somaliland. With the use of this method, recurrent themes and patterns in the dataset were found, illuminating insights into the experiences and perceptions of the participating parents and girls. Therefore, by extracting the key concepts, the following three main themes emerged:

- (1) Navigating Socio-economic Obstacles: Marginalized Girls' Journey to Higher Education in Hargeisa, Somaliland
- (2) Tradition vs. Progress: How Socio-Cultural Norms Shape Educational Accessibility for Marginalized Girls in Somaliland

(3) The Dearth of Scholarship Opportunities: A Significant Roadblock to Higher Education for Marginalized Girls

Theme 1: Navigating Socio-economic Obstacles: Marginalized Girls' Journey to Higher Education in Hargeisa, Somaliland

Several participants conveyed that socio-economic factors impact marginalized girls in access to higher education. Hence, three general themes identified from this theme are presented here:

1. Family Income, Relative Support, and Parental Roles

The family's income has an impact on the student's educational journey in one way or another. Some students always drop out of school due to the inability of their families. This is true when you see how education – in Somaliland, becomes expensive day after day.

In this regard, a respondent presented that family income has an effect on girls' educational opportunities, and she commented:

“When marginalized students graduate from secondary school, it becomes difficult to attend university. Because most of the families cannot afford the university fees. That is why some of my secondary classmates did not enter into a university” (Interviewee 7, a first-year university student).

But, with that income difficulties, some respondents presented the important role of parents particularly mothers play to support their girls in terms of pursuing their education. In the interview with a graduate girl, she stated:

“..... Although it was difficult for our family to manage the full educational costs of our children, our mother was the first person to fully support and inspire us to go forward with the financial hardships. I can say that is what enabled my younger sister and me to overcome the long journey until we reached our goal – to complete the bachelor's degree”. (Interviewee 13, a graduate girl).

Interviewee 4 illustrated the role of relatives when asked how their parents manage educational costs since some families cannot

cover all of their children's education, and she said:

"... My Mother always loves to see me learning. When my parents felt that they were not able to pay my university fees, she kindly requested her brother to cover my university fees. And fortunately, I graduated for my Mother's efforts through my Uncle". (Interviewee 4, a university student girl).

In the context of the marginalized community, parents work day-to-day small jobs to support their families' daily basic needs. Moreover, this paved the way for the struggle for their survival. As identified in 14 of the 22 interviews, this hinders them from sending their children to schools or universities. Talking about this issue, interviewee 9 illustrated:

"... Every day I go and work in the market to fulfill my obligation to support my wife and children. The daily income always is not enough to all of our needs. This causes me not to send some of my children to university and stay at home even though they completed secondary school because I cannot afford to pay \$200 - \$400 every few months". (Interviewee 9, a 47-year-old father).

2. Educational Level of Parents

The educational level of parents was a prominent theme, identified in 17 of the 22 interviews. Interviewee 1, a 22-year-old university student girl illustrated the role of the educational level of parents:

"Some parents did not have the opportunity to learn when they were young. As usual, they were ordered to safeguard the [family] animals. This becomes an obstacle to send their children to school compared to parents that had an educational opportunity". (Interviewee 1, a 22-year-old university student girl)

She explained the difference between parents in terms of their educational level and how this factor has helped some students get the opportunity to attend school. For example, Interviewee 19, a 51-year-old father, highlighted this.

"In my teenage at secondary school, the Somali civil war broke out. My dream to learn was interrupted. But, in this civilized world, we acknowledge the importance of education. Now I always strive for my children to learn". (Interviewee 19, a 51-year-old father)

A secondary student girl explained why some girls couldn't pursue their education, particularly at the secondary level, she illustrated:

"... Some girls drop out of school and never return since the parents' educational level is not enough to understand the educational challenges affecting their girls, this may be the reason". (Interviewee 20, an 18-year-old secondary student girl).

3. Type of Pre-tertiary Education

In Somaliland, the existing education context is through the public and private sectors. In this regard, to the best of the knowledge of the researcher, there is no research comparing the effectiveness of public and private schools in Somaliland. However, when asked during the interview which of the public and private schools they have attended, the majority of those who responded to this question presented that the number of girls who pursue their higher education are ones who graduated from private schools. This was described by Interviewee 10, a recent secondary graduate:

"As far as I know, during the four years we have been in secondary school, it is less likely to see girls from our community who have completed secondary school from public schools than private schools". (Interviewee 10, a recent secondary graduate).

On the other hand, Interviewee 16, a 45-year-old mother highlighted this.

"I prefer sending our girls to private than public school. Since private [schools'] fees are more expensive than public, one of my diaspora relatives covers these fees. And unless they support and stand with our children's education, they could have left the school since we had not afford to pay that fee". (Interviewee 16, a 45-year-old mother)

Theme 2: Tradition vs. Progress: How Socio-cultural Norms Shape Educational Accessibility for Marginalized Girls in Somaliland

Three broad themes emerged from the analysis, and they are here summarized.

1. Lack of Female Role Models

Accordingly, when the interviewed girls asked for those they make for themselves as role models, especially from their community, a university student girl highlighted:

“... We do not have effective female role models from our community those we can take their steps. And this In my opinion, may help a lot of marginalized girls to pursue their education and prioritize to achieve more success if there are female mentors”. (Interviewee 12, a university student girl)

She explained that the lack of female mentors from their respective community impact the self-esteem of young girls particularly those in their earlier educational journey. She wanted an explanation for having some effective female role models that would help marginalized girls to have confidence for their future. The need identified here is promoting marginalized girls to empower their potential and talents as future mentors.

2. Early Marriage

Under this theme, it has been addressed how early marriage and higher education for marginalized females relate to one another in the Somaliland context. Therefore, when asked why marginalized girls didn't pursue their higher education, most of the interviewees addressed that early marriage is one of the constraints as Interviewee 15, a university student girl stated:

“... The hardest part of our educational journey was the secondary level. This is where girls from our society always fail to pass because of getting married. For that reason, some girls lose interest in their education and they stop after marriage”. (Interviewee 15, a university student girl)

When the interviewees (both parents and girls) were asked about the possibility of working after the university graduate while the females are

married, the most surprising aspect of the responses that the majority commented on was that getting married with huge family roles also prevents them from being employed. Commenting on this issue, Interviewee 8, a university student girl discovered and said:

“... Although the number of marginalized females graduating from universities is very low, even those who completed their universities are not able to work whether in the public or private sectors because the younger girls believe that once they get married, they will not be able to continue her education or look for a job”. (Interviewee 8, a university student girl).

3. Facing Discriminations

It appears that the discrimination that marginalized girls experience while in school contributes to their failure to complete secondary education. Interviewee 18, a recent secondary school graduate girl asserted:

“...I did not encounter any discrimination from my teachers during my time in secondary school, although occasionally when we argue with our classmates (especially girls), they use discriminatory language towards us. As a result, some girls, like myself, were resistant, while others left the school and never returned”. (Interviewee 18, a recent secondary school graduate girl).

Theme 3: The Dearth of Scholarship Opportunities: A Significant Roadblock to Higher Education for Marginalized Girls

Globally, to improve access to education to achieve sustainable development, government and non-government scholarship programs for students pursuing graduate and postgraduate education must be available. However, in Somaliland, although reliable statistics are not yet available to assess the general situation of scholarship programs offered by public and private agencies to assist marginalized students in pursuing higher education, the scholarship suspension by the government to support these students has an impact on marginalized students' access in higher education, particularly girls. Explaining that, a 50-year-old interviewed parent revealed:

“...In general, the Somaliland government, particularly the Ministry of Finance and the public universities were providing scholarship opportunities to our secondary school graduates. When the scholarship programs were available, we were happy to see our children attending universities. But, unfortunately, the government suspended [scholarship opportunities] unexpectedly. This has affected students who graduated from secondary schools. But recently, although nothing has been fulfilled, the National Higher Education Committee promised to guarantee some of our children's higher educational scholarships”. (Interviewee 2, a 53-old-father).

Discussion

To the best of our knowledge, this research on the barriers, both stemming from traditional practices and contemporary challenges that hinder marginalized girls from accessing higher education is the first to be done in Somaliland. Prior studies have noted the importance of higher education for girls in general (Brown & James, 2020; Joshi, 2010).

Therefore, according to the aforementioned narratives, a family's income affects a girl's opportunity to attend a higher education. They were able to have accessibility thanks in part to such individual support, but not entirely.

According to the findings of the study, themes such as family income, relative support, and parental roles were drawn from the socio-economic factors in marginalized girls' access to higher education. Hence, regarding these, the study found that family income affects the accessibility to higher education. This causes them to face challenges in terms of paying university fees since they cannot afford to manage more students at the same time. Therefore, family income has been a major barrier for females around the world to access higher education and this is consistent with findings reported by (Narayan-Parker, 2002; Forsyth & Furlong, 2003; and Husen, 1976) who indicated that social inequalities and gender

disparities are most concerning barriers to marginalized girls' access to higher education.

Globally, numerous research in educational science, sociology, and economics have examined the effectiveness of public and private schools (Dronkers & Robert, 2003). For the type of pre-tertiary education, the study discovers that there are fewer girls from public schools who pursue their higher education than in private schools. Interviewees had a common feeling about their preference between private schools and public ones. This is not direct proof that private schools are better than public ones, but it is very important to know how private schools affect girls' chances of finishing their education.

As per the study results, the secondary level was the most challenging in marginalized girls' educational journey. But for those who complete their secondary are those graduates from the private schools. Even though the parents have put a lot of work into educating their girls, some of them still drop out of secondary school. Therefore, several studies indicated that parent education level has an impact on student dropout rates (e.g. Muhammad, 2015). In this regard, the education of the parents particularly the mother has a positive correlation with the performance and commitment of female students in school as reported by Development et al., (2016); Tuwor & Sossou, (2008).

Hence, the abovementioned narratives indicate that marginalized girls' dropping out of secondary schools especially those in public schools in Hargeisa Somaliland is one of the factors affecting their accessibility to higher education. These results are consistent with previous results reported by UNESCO (2012) which indicated that in most regions of the world, girls drop out of school at higher rates than boys do.

Socio-cultural factors that hinder marginalized girls' access to higher education, according to our findings, include lack of female mentors, early marriage customs, and prevalent discrimination. As such, marginalized girls require building their self-confidence, having role models, as well as financial support from

their families and the government. These findings further support the study results reported by Malik and Courtney (2011) who indicated that increasing the number of women who have access to higher education makes it possible for them to play bigger roles as role models in their families and communities. This also seems to be consistent with other research which found that girls and boys choose role models very differently from one another, both in terms of who they chose and why through their social behavior when choosing role models (Biskup & Pfister, 1999).

In addition, as some studies reported, this finding further supports the idea that the absence of female mentors makes it difficult for girls to continue in school and participate the school activities (Joseph et al., 2018).

In terms of early marriage, the study findings show that this is one of the main factors that thwart marginalized girls in Somaliland from having the opportunity to access higher education. These results are consistent with previous studies (e.g. Bosu & Dawson-Amoah, 2018; Gender in Somalia Brief II, 2015; Gul Khattak, 2019; Jama & Barre, 2019; Karlsson et al., 2007; Mansory, 2007) that found females' early school leaving was due to early marriage as a primary constrain due to family and parental roles when they are got married.

The educational gap for marginalized females in Somaliland is perpetuated by the continued discrimination against them based on their clans. According to how discrimination affects marginalized girls in their educational career, especially in secondary school, the study discovers that it causes some girls not to complete their secondary education, and that is a major constraint to their access to higher education. Therefore, this completely needs to change the attitude of the society to address the issue of discrimination and emphasize the need for social integration.

Themes on the scarce scholarship opportunities have shown that the Somaliland government has stopped scholarship opportunities for marginalized students. However, although the number of previously awarded scholarships was

not sufficient, but let some marginalized girls pursue their ambitions of attending universities. These results match those observed in earlier studies. For example, Tiwari (2020) reported that when the government of India initiated to consider some eligibility criteria, the impact of scholarships was limited. Hence, the study found that this issue needs to be addressed by increasing the number of available scholarships.

Conclusion

The study's exploration into the socioeconomic obstacles encountered by marginalized girls in Hargeisa, Somaliland, unveils a complex tapestry of challenges affecting access to higher education. The narratives bring forth the profound influence of family income and the vital support of parents and relatives on girls' educational journeys. The financial constraints and hardships, stemming from escalating education costs and daily struggles for survival in marginalized communities, are paramount, forcing many students to drop out of school. The struggle is not only financial; the educational level of parents, especially those who never had the opportunity to learn, becomes a substantial roadblock, influencing their capacity to support their children's education. The importance of relative support as a buffer against financial difficulties is highlighted, with instances of relatives stepping in to cover educational costs, emphasizing the community's role in fostering educational attainment.

Delving into socio-cultural norms and traditions, the study illuminates how these elements act as formidable barriers, shaping educational accessibility for marginalized girls. The lack of female role models is underscored as a significant impediment, affecting the self-esteem and aspirations of young girls. The study points out the urgent need for mentors from within the community, which could potentially empower marginalized girls, fostering their resilience and confidence. Early marriage is pinpointed as a crucial socio-cultural constraint, often resulting in girls losing interest in education post-marriage. The prevalent discrimination and societal attitudes towards marginalized

communities create an environment of resistance and adversity, with some girls resiliently fighting against it while others succumb and abandon their educational aspirations.

The study further sheds light on the critical role of scholarship opportunities, or rather the lack thereof, in marginalized girls' access to higher education. The suspension of scholarship programs by the government emerges as a significant setback, leaving many aspirants in a lurch, unable to continue their educational journey. The implications of this suspension are far-reaching, affecting the aspirations and access of marginalized students, especially girls, to higher education. The narratives echo a sense of loss and disappointment, emphasizing the pivotal role such scholarship programs play in bridging the financial gaps and making education accessible to the marginalized.

Implications and Reflections

In conclusion, the intricate interplay of socio-economic challenges, deeply entrenched socio-cultural norms, and the scarcity of institutional support creates a multifaceted barrier system, limiting marginalized girls' access to higher education in Hargeisa, Somaliland. The personal narratives and perceptions encapsulated in this study paint a vivid picture of the struggles, aspirations, and resilience of marginalized girls and their families. They highlight the urgent need for multifaceted interventions, encompassing community support, mentorship programs, and policy advocacy, aimed at dismantling these barriers and fostering an environment conducive to educational attainment for all. The findings underscore the imperative of reinstating scholarship programs, addressing socio-economic disparities, and altering prevailing discriminatory norms to pave the way for an equitable, inclusive, and progressive educational landscape in Somaliland. The study acts as a clarion call for collective action, policy reformation, and community engagement to uplift the marginalized and ensure equal access to education, thereby sowing

the seeds for sustainable development and societal progress in the region.

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Conflict of Interests

The researcher declares no conflict of interest.

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